

FROM WEB GRAPHS TO PRIORITIZING WEB CRAWLS

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Extended Abstract

This talk describes how web graphs are used at Common Crawl to prioritize which sites and pages are visited by the crawler.

The Common Crawl data sets are sample collections of web pages with no intention to mirror websites completely. In order to achieve a balanced, both diverse and representative sample, the crawler is "steered" to web sites found to be relevant by analyzing the hyperlink structure of preceding crawls. Harmonic centrality and page rank scores are calculated on hyperlink graphs and define the authority of a web site both on the level of hosts and registered domains. The authority is then mapped to a likelihood that a URL from the corresponding site is sampled and to a "crawl budget" which limits the max. number of pages crawled.

The talk will cover the following points:

1. we start with a short introduction of Common Crawl, the goals and give an overview of the crawl technology used between 2008 and 2021.
2. we present the Common Crawl in-house webgraphs and rankings (2017 until now) and how they are constructed, starting from the extraction of hyperlinks, the aggregation on the level of host and domain names and the transformation into a numeric graph representation. We will also look into prior work of building hyperlink graphs from the Common Crawl: page ranks used in the 2012 crawl and earlier, the graphs and rankings from the "Web Data Commons" and "Common Search" projects, and the webgraph framework developed at the University of Milano.
3. the Common Crawl rankings are compared with other open accessible web site rankings – the top-1-million sites published by Alexa, the "Cisco Umbrella Popularity" list, "The Majestic Million" and the Tranco list.
4. we show how the authority of a site in terms of the harmonic centrality rank is used
5. to sample hyperlinks,
6. to define a "crawl budget" per domain (how many web pages or subdomains the crawler is allowed to crawl from this domain)
7. and how domain-level score can be projected to the level of web pages
8. we discuss the challenges associated with the use of link-based centrality measures, namely link spam and other attempts (eg. aggressive SEO) to influence the domains ranks by artificially creating sites, pages and hyperlinks. We look into a few spam clusters, demonstrate how these can be identified and which strategies can be used to prevent the crawler from hitting and getting trapped in spam clusters.
9. finally, we evaluate how the usage of centrality measures impacts the crawled data:
 - a. we outline the preliminaries and constraints of the Common Crawl data sets: the focus on HTML pages and the 1 MiB content limit, the impact of operating a crawler from a data center in North America, the need for sampling and shuffling and the immediate release of the data.
 - b. multiple aspects of representativity are discussed in order to define an evaluation baseline: the domain-level coverage compared to different crawling strategies (breadth-first, depth-first), regional coverage (top-level domains, content languages), the amount of duplicates and other.
 - c. we analyze the crawls 2017 – 2021 and evaluate how the crawled data fits the various aspects of representativity.